

Real-time cattle behavior tracking in pasture using computer vision and deep learning

Authors: Said Benaissa, Pieter-Jan De Temmerman, Sacha Coussement, and Jarissa Maselyne

Organisation: Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO)

Keywords: Behavior monitoring, deep learning, computer vision, livestock farming, pasture, health and welfare monitoring

Introduction

Incorporating pasture access into dairy production systems provides substantial benefits, such as promoting natural behaviors (e.g., grazing and resting) [1], enhancing animal health and welfare by reducing occurrence of diseases like lameness and mastitis [3], and lowering feed costs [2]. Modern Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) systems can support the adoption of pasture livestock farming by enabling real-time and long-term monitoring of livestock. Consequently, farmers can ensure optimal nutrition of their animals and detect health issues early.

Wearable-based monitoring systems, including accelerometers and GPS collars, have been extensively used in precision livestock farming (PLF) systems [4,5]. These systems offer advantages like individual animal tracking and activity pattern recognition. However, challenges such as high costs, limited battery life, and data transmission constraints in outdoor environments hinder their scalability.

Alternatively, computer vision-based monitoring systems offer a cost-effective and scalable solution [6]. Using cameras, these systems can monitor multiple animals simultaneously, capturing their locations, behaviors, and welfare indicators [6]. These insights enable farmers to make data-driven decisions, such as adjusting feed distribution, detecting early signs of health issues, and improving overall herd management efficiency [6]. Recent advancements in computer vision and deep learning, such as the YOLOv8 model, have enabled robust and efficient detection and tracking of animals in complex outdoor environments.

Building on previous work [7] that focused on cattle localization using computer vision, this article extends the methodology to detect grazing behaviors (i.e., grazing, lying, and standing) in real-time. This innovation addresses a critical gap in behavior monitoring and provides actionable insights for PLF systems in pasture farming.

Behavior Detection

The development of the system relied on a robust combination of advanced computer vision techniques and efficient edge computing to ensure real-time processing capabilities in outdoor environments. A high-resolution USB camera (Daheng MER2-302-56U3C, Daheng Group, Beijing, China), mounted six meters above the ground, captured video data of grazing cattle over a 1-hectare pasture. Approximately 2 TB of video footage were collected across varying weather conditions to ensure the system's reliability and adaptability. From this dataset, 12578 images were manually annotated to label individual cows (using a bounding box) and three behaviors: grazing, lying, and standing.

The YOLOv8 model [8] was selected for its high performance in object detection and adaptability to real-world applications. This model was fine-tuned to recognize cattle and classify their behaviors using bounding box annotations. By leveraging its robust architecture, YOLOv8 efficiently distinguished subtle differences between behaviors that often overlap visually.

To enable real-time processing, the system was optimized for edge computing. The video streams were processed locally using the Nvidia Jetson Orin Nano board. This board was chosen for its balance of computational power and energy efficiency, making it suitable for solar-powered setups. The Jetson Orin Nano features a 6-core ARM Cortex-A78AE CPU, a 1024-core Ampere GPU, and 32 TOPS (Tera Operations Per Second) of AI performance, enabling it to process up to 60 frames per second of 1080p video. With a typical power consumption of 7-15W, it can operate efficiently on solar power, handling high-throughput video streams while maintaining a sustainable energy footprint. The data was then transmitted to an InfluxDB database via a 4G network, ensuring seamless data integration for downstream analysis and visualization. The local processing significantly reduced latency and allowed the system to function independently of cloud-based services, making it suitable for remote farm environments.

Figure 1 shows an example of the behavior detection by the Yolov8 model. Initial results demonstrated an overall classification accuracy of 97%, with lying behavior achieving the highest precision and recall scores (98%) followed by grazing and standing behaviors (91-97%). The system's ability to process data locally and transmit summarized behavior patterns ensures both operational efficiency and data integrity, positioning it as a scalable solution for real-time livestock monitoring.

Figure 1. Behaviors of grazing cows detected by the Yolov8 model.

Future Developments

Future developments aim to expand the dataset with diverse environments and additional animals to enhance model robustness and reduce overfitting while exploring alternative algorithms like Vision Transformers [9] for improved behavior classification and pose estimation. These efforts align with

other XGain use cases, such as improving connectivity for precision aquaculture monitoring, deploying edge computing for remote forestry management, and utilizing IoT solutions to optimize resource allocation in rural farming. Integrating solar panels into the setup will ensure a sustainable power supply, reducing environmental impact and operational costs. Tracking individual animals over time will provide detailed behavior analysis and health monitoring, and combining computer vision data with remote sensing technologies will enable comprehensive assessments of pasture quality and animal health. These enhancements will further refine the system's scalability, accuracy, and environmental sustainability, making it a critical tool in advancing precision livestock farming.

Conclusion

This study highlights the potential of computer vision and deep learning for real-time cattle behavior monitoring in pasture-based systems, enabling farmers to make data-driven decisions such as early detection of health issues, optimizing grazing management, and improving overall animal welfare. The YOLOv8 model's high accuracy in behavior detection paves the way for scalable and cost-effective solutions in precision livestock farming. By addressing challenges such as dataset diversity and renewable energy integration, future developments aim to enhance the system's reliability and sustainability. This work represents a significant step toward data-driven animal welfare management in agriculture.

XGain

References

1. Arnott, G., Ferris, C.P., & O'Connell, N.E. (2017). Welfare of dairy cows in continuously housed and pasture-based production systems. *Animal*, 11(2), 261-273.
2. Dartt, B. A., Lloyd, J. W., Radke, B. R., Black, J. R., & Kaneene, J. B. (1999). A comparison of profitability and economic efficiencies between management- intensive grazing and conventionally managed dairy farms in Michigan. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 82(11), 2412-2420. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(99\)75491-5](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(99)75491-5)
3. Haskell, M. J., Rennie, L. J., Bowell, V. A., Bell, M. J., & Lawrence, A. B. (2006). Housing system, milk production, and zero-grazing effects on lameness and leg injury in dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 89(11), 4259-4266. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(06\)72472-9](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(06)72472-9)
4. Neethirajan, S. (2020). Recent advances in wearable sensors for animal health management. *Sensing and Bio-Sensing Research*, 29, 100358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbsr.2020.100358>
5. Tobin, C., Bailey, D. W., Trotter, M. G., & O'Connor, L. J. (2020). The potential of GPS tracking for monitoring and understanding the grazing behavior of livestock. *Animals*, 10(11), 2026. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10112026>
6. Mahmud, M.S., Zahid, A., Das, A.K., Muzammil, M., & Khan, M.U. (2021). Deep learning applications for precision cattle farming. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 187, 106313.
7. Haumont, J., De Temmerman, P.-J., Vangeyte, J., & Maselyne, J. (2024). Localization of grazing cows using Yolov8 object detection and known landmarks. *European Conference on Precision Livestock Farming*, September 2024.
8. Jocher, G., Chaurasia, A., & Qiu, J. (2023). Ultralytics YOLOv8. Available at: GitHub.
9. Xu, Y., et al. (2024). ViTPose++: Vision Transformer for Generic Body Pose Estimation. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 46(2), 1212-1230.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA) (granting authority). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.